

Impact of Empowerment on Employee's Psychological Wellbeing

Author's Details: ⁽¹⁾ Azhar khan (Assistant Professor) Northern University, Nowshera ⁽²⁾Shafqat Ali Bangash (Lecturer) Northern University, Nowshera ⁽³⁾Mubashir Ahmad (Assistant Professor) Northern University, Nowshera ⁽⁴⁾Fahad Ali Khan (Assistant Professor) Northern University, Nowshera KP, Pakistan

Abstract

Empowerment as a positive triggering instrument in employees which is also considered an integral and vital part of employee's psychological wellbeing. Empowerment results in productivity, satisfaction and determination of the employees working for an organization provided that it is properly monitored and there is a check and balance system. Psychological well-being includes the wellness and fitness and well-being of particular people in the office. Quantitative research was carried out with the aim to find the impact of empowerment on employee's psychological wellbeing. Adopted questionnaire was used for the collection of primary data. Random sample techniques were used. In this regards, data was collected from 50 executive level employees of Pakistan State Oil and Attock Refinery Limited. Two hypotheses were tested by using regression analysis. The value of R shows .461 correlations between empowerment and psychological wellbeing. R^2 shows the impact of empowerment (Independent variable) on psychological wellbeing (Dependent variable). According to the results of regression, Model 1 ($F = 12.924, p < 0.001$), were statistically significant. The coefficient of empowerment was positive and significant at 1 percent. It means that empowerment has statistically significant impact on Psychological wellbeing. The value of F statistics is about 13 and the P value 0.00 it means that the model was fit to predict. The value R^2 is 21 percent states that about 21 percent change in the psychological employee wellbeing is due to the empowerment, the remaining 79 percent changes in the employee psychological wellbeing is due to other factors which is unexplained by this model. So the analysis reject the null hypothesis that state that empowerment has no impact on employee psychological wellbeing. And accepted alternative hypothesis of this study which was "Empowerment have positive impact on Employee Psychological Wellbeing". Company identified a positive relationship between empowerment and psychological wellbeing. The finding of this study shows that company should empower employees to give them that psychological feeling is being committed to the organization. Committed to an organization is strength because psychological empowerment plays a vital role in commitment of employees towards that every organization.

Key words: Empowerment, Psychological wellbeing.

Introduction

Background Information

In today's dynamic and volatile environment as the customer's needs and wants are expanding and varying from each perspective, it is quite a challenging task to address those needs and fulfill them efficiently. Considering the diversity in needs and wants, the employers are under immense pressure to perform with their best abilities to get the job done in this diverse atmosphere of serving the needs of customers. Hence the employees are motivated with a number of agendas and motivational steps to make them more efficient and profitable. Under such motivational schemes and steps employee empowerment has grown to become an important factor and has attained all the required attention among the organizations around the globe. An empowered employee has the tendency to feel strong from within and feel the autonomy and control in his favor. Thus the empowered employees feel more committed and devoted to their nature of work as compared to those who is less empowered.

Empowerment as a positive triggering instrument in employees is also considered an integral and vital part of employee's psychological wellbeing. However the true essence of such factors are discussed ahead by a considerable inter relation of cut factors on job and employee wellbeing.

Empowerment

Empowerment relates control over material assets, intellectual resources and ideology. It involves power to, power with and power within. Some define empowerment as a process of awareness and conscientization, of capacity building leading to greater participation, effective decision-making power and control leading to transformative action (Singhal, 2015).

Empowerment has emerged as an important concept from the 1980's and therefore has been an important idea for practitioners and academics because of the fact that after two decades of research it has been found that job

performance and job satisfaction can be enhanced through empowerment. (Michael K Hui', Kevin Au and Henry Fock, 2004)

The meaning of the term empowerment according to the initial studies was limited just to the delegating of decision making powers from the top level of the organization to the lower levels (Grethchen M. Spreitzer 1995) whereas now a few decades later researchers believe that it has a wide range of meanings, perception and interpretation varying with culture and it ranges from psychological to philosophy to motivational sciences (Rappaport, 1987).

Empowerment can result in increase in productivity, satisfaction and determination of the employees working for an organization provided that it is properly monitored and there is a check and balance system. There are three levels of empowerment namely Individual, group and environmental/action, for each there are certain specific components which are important for the empowerment process. For example at the individual level self-confidence & self-worth are important, similarly sense of belonging and interpersonal relationships at the group level and learning, publicity and raised expectations at the environmental level (Elizabeth Whitmore, 1990).

For the increase in productivity, creativity & innovation it is important that there is a proper implementation of empowerment programs where authority is delegated to the deserving employees, so that the employee can then start taking initiatives to act on their own and become more entrepreneurial. According to (Fulford & Cathy, 1995) by empowering people with the ultimate objective of increasing productivity, it also leads to greater customer satisfaction.

Employee Psychological Wellbeing

Psychological well-being has two facets: eudaimonic well-being and hedonic well-being (Ryan and Deci, 2000).

The eudaimonic well-being refers to the purposeful aspect of psychological well-being (Johnson et al., 2018), and Ryff developed six dimensions of eudaimonic well-

being that widely used until recently (Yoon, Coburn and Spence, 2018). The hedonic well-being refers to the subjective feelings of happiness, subjective well-being and positive emotions (Johnson et al., 2018).

Harris et al. (2017) reviewed 26 relevant studies on stereotypes about older workers and found that stereotypes and perceptions were negative, although positive and negative beliefs coexisted. In 23 studies, older workers perceived as lacking in productivity and ability, based on a negative perception of their ability to use new technologies and their

Psychological well-being physical and mental capacity (Harris et al., 2017).

Wellbeing of the employees include Quality of work-life that is supporting work-life balance, physical wellbeing, mental wellbeing, social wellbeing and providing a safe and conducive work environment. For a successful and productive workforce employers are now focusing more on health and wellness initiatives of their employees (Worldatwork, 2012). The wellbeing that is referred in this text is about the inbound personal goals of human being as so the work force and environment shall not at any cost interfere with the personal inbound space dedicated to family and friends.

A large text of literature about wellbeing at workplace is available connecting the satisfaction and quality of work place together (Warr 1999). The wellbeing at work place is also quantified in the context of workplace quality for some matter as well. The main essence of this term is to increase the efficiency of employees. Studies have pointed out the inter relation between quality of working life towards employee's attitude and output. The concepts like lowering steam of non-agreement among employee and the firm, the concept of scaled centered leadership and enlargement of working task are considered remedies of low performing employee or work force. (Argyris, 1957).

For example psychological well-being has been connected in different way with the outcomes of job and life. Wright & Hay (1999) associated Psychological well-being with the outcomes of the performance of a person at an organization. Diener & Seligman (2002) connected Psychological well-being alongside with a successful relationship among themselves. In addition to that it was linked with physical condition and survival as well (Royasamb, 2003).

Research Statement

The focus of this study is to find if there is an impact of empowerment on the wellbeing of the employees in Oil and Gas sector (Pakistan state oil and Attock refinery limited).

Scope

The scope of this study is limited to Peshawar, Islamabad and Rawalpindi and it is carried out on the two companies of the Oil and Gas sector i.e. Pakistan state oils and Attock refinery limited. The results of the study are limited to the regions mentioned above.

Purpose

The purpose of this research is to find whether empowerment has an impact on the wellbeing of the employees in Attock Refinery limited and Pakistan State Oil. Empowerment has a powerful essence on the productivity factor of wellbeing since it is associated with the psychological wellbeing of the employees. The studies are subjected to form a harmony of these variables and its impacts on the organization productivity and employee output ratio.

Literature Review

In the following paragraphs, empowerment, wellbeing and its relationship is discussed in the light of the existing literature.

Empowerment has been a prominent idea for researchers and organizational since its late appearance on the scale of notice since 1980. The word empowerment has to be used for more obvious purpose in every context.

The working service employees are constantly at scrutiny on account of the fact that they have to fulfill their clients' needs considering the organizational goals and guidelines in line with each other, any non-agreement of clients request and organization code of conducts can add up to clients discontentment hence to avoid any disagreement the firm should endorse the service provider and front line worker with some power to exercise and feel motivated. To make the front line workers life easier on the working tasks, they have to be given some authority and autonomy (Eileen K. Hui, Kevin Au, and Gretchen Fock 2004).

Empowerment can be described as giving a worker relevant power and autonomy in calling decisions, which make it easier of the worker to make fluent decisions at time when it matters. (Robbins, Chatterjee, & Canda, 1998). Around the mid 80's, the term empowerment snatched the interest of the many experts and supervisors around the world and was measured a well-organized tool for improving job achievement (Gretchen M. Spreitzer, 1995).

Singhal (2015) stated empowerment is a process that enables person to gain access to, and control of, material, intellectual and human resources. Empowerment is the re-distribution of power that challenges patriarchal ideology (Singhal, 2015).

Greasley, K; Byrman, A.; Petite, A.; Price, A. Naismith, N; Soetanto, R. (2008) suggested two typical view points, starting as structural empowerment. It represents the power sharing between the workers and their subordinates. If powers are allocated similarly it increases trusts and contributes to cooperation. However in some organizations it is considered that even after empowerment workers feel disempowered and less inspired hence the company has to cover all the factors of empowerment to get to the forecasted result. The follow up perspective was psychological power, which concerns with the individual worker. The psychologically motivated condition were supposed to be an intellectual condition recognized by a sense of recognized power and views of proficiency.

Empowerment has been described in one of the following two methods. The first talks about empowerment as a power sharing sets, managing strategies, methods and techniques (Thomas and Velthouse 1990; Honda and Fottler 1995; Wilkinson 1998; Eylon and Bamberger 2000; Forrester 2000; Walls, Cordery et al. 2002). For others, empowerment delegates discretion to reduced business stages and allow workers to manage their own projects. Team empowerment is determined as the variety of choices the group is permitted to make to be able to meet up with its aim (Gerwin 1999).

The second meaning originates from an intellectual viewpoint and signifies the inspirational condition of workers (Thompson 1967; Thomas and Velthouse 1990; Spreitzer 1995 and 1996; Kirkman and Rosen. 1997; Eylon and Bamberger 2000; Kirkman, Rosen et al. 2004). Spreitzer (1995 and 1996) designed empowerment with regards to multidimensional constructs catching four cognitions of personal alignment, namely, meaningfulness, proficiency, self-determination, and effect, according to Johnson and Velthouse (1990). However, Forrester (2000) suggests that one of factors of the failing of empowerment system is "over-reliance on a filter emotional idea of empowerment" (P68). He suggested that the idea developing emotional empowerment as a sustained psychological function of workers is impractical. In comparison, empowerment as a managing exercise provides obvious, realistic significance for supervisors and workers.

Psychological empowerment is another essential construct that can possibly create profitable enterprise and individual stage results. There are several viewpoints on empowerment, such as relational, social-structural, and psychological (Liden, Sparrowe, & John, 1997).

Depending on an evaluation of content on the topic of psychological well-being, Wright and Cropanzano (2000) determined that psychological health problems have never been as essential as they are these days. Due to the fast speed of transformation of working nature and the needs and wants paradigm shift of employees and customers, the well-being of the employee may be at threat because of the immense uncertainty, volatile environment and numerous organizational needs (Kinnunen, Geurts, & Mauno, 2004). Focusing on the psychological wellbeing of the workers is essential because it impacts their behavior, decision making and communications with co-workers, and also spills over to members of the family and social life. (Warr, 1990, 1987).

According to Keyes, Hysom and Lupo (2000), wellbeing represents employees' understanding and evaluation of the high quality of their lives, and the high quality of their psychological and social performing. As worker well-being improves, the efficiency, and success of the organization also increase (Warr, 1999). But when worker well-being reduces stress will increase and the chances for dealing effectively with stresses will reduce (Cox, 1987).

Mentally healthy people experience thrilled and relying on connections, think that they are creating as people, have an objective in their lifestyles, think that they can shape the world around them to fit their needs, and experience capable to immediate their activities from inner requirements. Individuals who experience high well-being are generally excellent decision creators, illustrate better social behaviors, and receive higher overall performance scores (Wright & Cropanzano, 2004). Workers who are more pleased with their lifestyles and factors of their work are more co-operative and helpful to their co-workers, more prompt, review less fed up days, and remain employed for a longer period than more dissatisfied employees (Spector, 1997; Warr, 1999).

Psychological well-being includes the wellness and fitness and well-being of particular people in the office. While enterprise well-being is important to the achievements of companies, it is almost difficult to obtain without promoting psychological well-being among workers.

Richmond and co-workers (2006) describe that job-related pressure and job discontentment is obvious in those who perform in surroundings with little managing assistance. Actually, in a study of over 90,000 workers, management's attention in the well-being of workers was one of the primary aspects for inspiration (Gallup, 2011). The query then becomes: how do we develop an office loaded with improved psychological well-being? What can supervisors do to make sure that their workers are satisfied and healthy?

There are many ways that supervisors can strategize this issue. The 2012 Sodexo Office Styles Report outlines various methods in which control can concentrate upon worker health and fitness, such as (1) clearly revealing objectives, (2) enabling versatility in operations, (3) acknowledging workers for their initiatives, and (4) offering possibilities for self-improvement within businesses can have a serious effect on employees' inspiration and job fulfillment. All of these elements tie into the psychological well-being of employees.

Psychological well-being is mostly described with regards to the overall efficiency of a person's emotional performance (Gechman & Weiner, 1975; Jamal & Mitchell, 1980; Martin, 1984; Sekaran, 1985). More particularly, on the reasons for the model of emotions, psychological well-being speculates the hedonic or pleasantness sizing of personal emotions (J. A. vnbRussell, 1980; J. A. Russell, Weiss, & Mendelsohn, 1989). Medical specialists have lengthily identified the part of the pleasantness sizing of well-being (i.e., happiness vs. unhappiness or depression) in the dedication of various personal results. For example, frustrated people have very low self-esteem, are generally negative, and display decreased inspiration and slowed down thoughts (Holmes, 1991; Wright & Bonett, 1997). Additionally, as compared with job fulfillment, which is based on the performance perspective in the workplace, psychological well-being is a global construct. Most generally, psychological well-being is based on individual and separate terms just like job fulfillment which is not related to any scenario (Kornhauser, 1965; Warr, 1987, 1990).

Like their medical mindset and public health alternatives, business advocates have also long identified the comprehensive costs, in both human and financial terms, because of worker structural psychological well-being (Henry, 1992; Fast, Fast, Nelson, & Hurrell, 1997). For example, depressive disorders, self-esteem deprivation, high blood pressure, alcohol addiction, and drug intake has been linked to structural wellbeing (Ivancevich & Matteson, 1980). Because they have a direct influence on performance of an employee (Fast et al., 1997), it is however probable and possible that all these factors are even in relevance with each other (Wright, Bonett, & Sweeney, 1993).

A number of other two studies by Wright also argued links between performance of an employee at workplace and the wellbeing of that particular employee. Wright (1993) also found out that the superior sub ordinate scores also mattered in job performance. In another analysis, Wright and Bonett (1997) also discovered an important connection between employee performance and wellbeing at workplace. Moreover, past analysis has revealed an important connection between well-being and job fulfillment (e.g., Diener et al., 1999; Assess & Locke, 1993). Nonetheless, till date, no released scientific analysis has achieved relative test of job fulfillment and emotional well-being as outcome of performance. There have been many researches and evidences about a significant relationship between meaning full work and its impact on psychological wellbeing of employees and the transformational leadership associated with the overall relation. If however, meaningful work is considered a means for transformational leadership and it is considered to put positive weight on psychological well-being, we have to acknowledge the declaration that significant effort is somehow associated to psychological well-being. Many authors have described relating meaning from situations as a “fundamental human motive” (Britt, Adler, & Bartone, 2001). The reward of observing sense in situation range from an increased will to live (Frankl, 1963) to suggesting and hoping payback in certain demanding actions (Britt et al., 2001). With respect to work, finding job after leaving school shall have optimistic impact on psychological well-being (Winefield & Tiggemann, 1990). Compared with the students who are unemployed, on the job employers displayed more optimistic results as compared to others. In another case study, built-in reason for functioning (i.e., considering the act of work more productive) was observed to be directive of intention to work with a set of individuals who were suffering from a terminal illness (Westaby, Versenyi, & Hausmann, 2005).

Psychological well-being is generally considered as an affect-based assembles (Warr, 1987) and a regular and constant feature (Wright & Bonett, 1997). It has been recommended that impact may be a determinant of innovative achievements on a theoretical stage (Amabile, 1988), but the analysis performed in the area of creativeness has ignored the impact of impact on creativity (Damanpour, 1991). The analysis that has been performed in this field has proven that beneficial impacts that are caused in lab settings can improve creativeness (Isen, 1999a, b; Isen et al., 1987) and that because psychological wellbeing carefully faucets the hedonic or pleasure sizing, it is predictive of creativeness (Isen et al., 1987; Wright & Walton, 2003). To the information of the writer the connection between well-being and creativity has not yet been examined in business analysis configurations.

Stress is one of the most regularly revealed, work-related issues across Europe (Paoli & Merllie, 2000). One of the most essential resources to stress has been determined as changes of various kinds. Modify is not always welcomed by the workers (Beer & Nohria, 2000) and has been associated with wellness repercussions among workers (Vahtera, Kivimäki, Pentti, 1997; Westerland, Ferrie, Hagberg, Jeding, Oxenstierna, Theorell, 2004). In Beer and Nohria’s research (2000) 70% of change projects were met with resistance and as an impact was unsuccessful. Vakola and Nikolaou (2005) showed that change is often met with adverse behavior as it delivers stress and uncertainty.

If the stress that employees are experiencing is not handled, it can give rise to greater absenteeism, turn over (Gupta & Beehr, 1979), an inability to adjust to new circumstances longer and more regular fed up results in, and conflicts between employees and or control (LeCraw, 1992), decreased work performance and efficiency, greater levels of injuries, and employee complaints (Cox & Griffiths, 1995a), job-dissatisfaction, exhaustion, and tension (Beehr, Walsh, & Taber, 1976), and burnout, stress, high blood pressure, as well as heart illnesses (Landy & Conte, 2004; Selye, 1976). Lazarus (1991) considered stress as an continuous process in which an individual makes an intellectual evaluation of the scenario and an evaluation of available resources the person have or encounters that he or she have to deal with the stresses in the scenario. Thus, when one encounters situations traumatic or harmful and creates the reasoning that one does not have the potential to cope with the problem, one encounters stress. Stressors are usually termed as actual or emotional requirements that individuals respond to. Common stresses at the office include for example amount of work, time stress, part indecisiveness, social disputes, lack of control, and more actual stresses such as warm, disturbance, cold etc.(Landy & Conte, 2004).

However, it is to be mentioned that it is the potential or capability of our reasoning that decides whether we will experience the scenario as traumatic or manageable.

Though not all stress stages are adverse, actually a certain level of pressure has shown to be an important part of life that makes us operate and perform our best. According to the Yerkes-Dodson Law, developed by Yerkes and Dodson (1908), performance as well as improves with increase in stress, but only to a certain point. When stress becomes too great, it affects performance, and performance usually decreases. Stress becomes adverse

when it surpasses an individual's potential to handle and deal and it results in an inhibited performance at execute. The use of execute stresses is considered to be associated with generally low stages of emotional well-being (Cox & Griffiths, 1995a). If the adverse pressure improves, the well-being of the employees and their potential to successfully deal with stresses decreases (Cox, 1987). In reality, deficiency of well-being has been found to be expected by work stresses (Cooper, Rout, & Faraghar, 1989).

Bradburn's (1969) traditional perform on the framework of psychological well-being offered the preliminary difference between positive and adverse impact. The aim of this analysis was to understand how certain macro level public changes (e.g., changes in education levels, career styles, urbanization, or governmental tensions) affected the lifestyle circumstances of individual citizens and, in turn, their feeling of psychological well-being.

Conceptual Framework

There are two variables in this research. Empowerment is act as (independent variable) while Psychological wellbeing is act as (dependent variable).

Hypothesis of the research

H0: Empowerment has negative impact on Employee Psychological Wellbeing

H1: Empowerment have positive impact on Employee Psychological Wellbeing

Research Methodology

In this phase the methodology is used to conduct the study.

Research philosophy

A research philosophy denoted as the set of principles concerning the nature and reality being scrutinized (Bryman, 2012). Research philosophy can be positivism and interpretivism. Positivism philosophy is concerning with highly quantifiable observations and to analyze the results by using statistics tools. The present study is based on positivism philosophy as hypotheses were tested to interpret statistical results.

Research approach

The research approach can be inductive or deductive. This study is deductive as two hypotheses are tested to find the results.

Research strategy

It can be descriptive, explanatory or exploratory. This study is explanatory as the variables of the study is being explained by the researcher.

Research choice

Choice is based on the aim of the study. The choice can be qualitative or quantitative. This study is conducted with the aim to find the impact of empowerment on psychological wellbeing. This study was conducted quantitatively as data was obtained in numeric terms.

Observational Strategy

It can be refers to the cross-sectional or longitudinal observational. This study is basically cross sectional study as researcher went to the field and collected primary data at one shot span of time.

Data collection method

It is the most important process of research. Normally primary and secondary data is required to proceed analysis. In this study, primary data is collected from the field via questionnaire.

Tool for fact finding

Psychological well-being Psychological well-being was measured using Ryff's (1995) six dimensions. Each subscale consists of seven items measured using a seven-point Likert scale ranging from (1) strongly disagree to (7) strongly agree.

And Empowerment was measured by Spreitzer G.M 1995, Psychological Empowerment at work scale.

Population:

The population of this research is executive level employees of Pakistan State Oil (PSO) and Attock Refinery Limited (ARL). According to review of literature, the said area has been ignored by researchers while almost banking sector is the main focused are of every researcher

Sample Size:

After determining the overall population of the Pakistan state Oil (PSO) Peshawar Office and Attock Refinery Limited (ARL) Rawalpindi Office the total population of executive level officers were observed 150 of both companies. 50 executives are randomly selected which is the 33% of the total population.

Sampling Technique:

Random sampling technique is carried out for the collection of primary data.

Data Collection

Primary data was gathered through questionnaire from Attock Refinery Limited (ARL) and Pakistan State Oil (PSO).

Analysis

In this study, a simple linear regression is used to find the Impact of empowerment and psychological wellbeing. The analyses of the results are given in the tables below:

Table 1

Variables Entered/Removed^a

Model	Variables Entered	Variables Removed	Method
1	Empowerment	.	Enter

a. Dependent Variable: Psychological wellbeing

b. All requested variables entered.

Table 2

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.461 ^a	.212	.196	.29783

a. Predictors: (Constant), Empowerment

The above table 2 indicates Model Summary, the value of R shows .461 correlation between empowerment and psychological wellbeing. R² shows the impact of empowerment (Independent variable) on psychological wellbeing (Dependent variable). Adjusted R square after reducing error were found .196.

Table 3

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1.146	1	1.146	12.924	.001 ^b
	Residual	4.258	48	.089		
	Total	5.404	49			

a. Dependent Variable: Psychological wellbeing

b. Predictors: (Constant), Empowerment

According to the results of regression, Model1 (F = 12.924, p<0.001), were statistically significant. As the independent variable R2 was found .212.

Table 4

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	3.104	.313		9.906	.000
	Empowerment	.209	.058	.461	3.595	.001

a. Dependent Variable: Psychological wellbeing

The coefficient of empowerment is positive and is significant at 1 percent. It means that empowerment has statistically significant impact on Psychological wellbeing. The value of F statistics is about 13 and the P value 0.00 it means that the model is fit to predict. The value R² is 21 percent states that about 21 percent change in the psychological employee wellbeing is due to the empowerment, the remaining 79 percent changes in the employee psychological wellbeing is due to other factors which is unexplained by this model. So the analysis reject the null hypothesis that state that empowerment has no impact on employee psychological wellbeing.

Therefore it can be safely concluded that wellbeing has a significant role in the employee morale building and can be considered equally vital alongside the other factors such as incentives and salary which drive the productivity factor of employee and make them work hard and efficient at a standardized pace.

Discussion, Conclusion and Recommendations

Discussion:

All the findings described in this research concur that wellbeing is not only associated with employees health only but it also yields in confronting employee to work hard and be as efficient as his abilities demand. Even though productivity should be the main concern for any firm but when it comes to wellbeing of employee than the health factor also come in line with the productivity factor as Illness of an employee and distressed worker is as harmful to the firm as a non-efficient employee. We should also bear that in mind that the high estimated cost of illness and early deaths of employee cause considerable loss to any firm. Beside sick leaves and less productivity are only the indirect costs of poor wellbeing.

Besides these cost factors there are positive aspect of empowerment and wellbeing to an employee of any firm that is by keeping all the measure in align to the achievement which triggers the high productivity and outcome of an employee, when the employers get the job done from the workers. It's a rational parameter considering the reward which is equally beneficial to the employee, employer and the organization. This study not only clarified the term empowerment but also added knowledge to any firm. There are mostly two areas of influence with such contribution. "First, there is the interpretation of personal control. Most of the literature connects empowerment with personal control (Rapp port, 1987). The workers interviewed in this study echoed their anxiety for control as they described their struggles. Other literature describes control in terms of coping (Epp, 1986; World Health Organization, 1986). Secondly according to Bandura (1986) very little has been said about the relationship between self-efficacy and empowerment in the available literature of empowerment. In our findings employees have pointed towards a positive change in themselves alongside external sources of empowerment and people support.

Conclusion

The study was carried out to find whether empowerment has an impact on the psychological wellbeing of employees in Pakistan State Oil (PSO) and Attock Refinery Limited (ARL) Company identified a positive relationship between empowerment and psychological wellbeing. The finding of this study is not merely carried out for the very specific organization rather it shows that organizations should empower employees to give them that psychological feeling is being committed to the organization. Committed to an organization is strength because psychological empowerment plays a vital role in commitment of employees towards that every organization. It is a very common phenomena that if you want to get something, you will have to invest something. Empowerment psychologically should be given the perception of meaningful tasks, autonomy in work; feeling of skillfulness in performing tasks will lead to high level of organizational commitment. Therefore, organizations must provide the employees with such a platform that is not only satisfactory but it should also lead to psychological empowerment. By giving the respective authority to managers for which they demand for and which is rational for their responsibility and which fall rightfully in the domain of their working boundaries is a useful tool for the organization. There is nothing more profitable and competitive advantage for a firm to have a workforce that is out of the ordinary confident and this confidence is well immersed on their output and working efficiency.

Recommendations for future research

First, future research needs to consider adopting a longitudinal design. In order to clarify causal relationships between variables, it is necessary to utilize longitudinal data. In particular, as empowerment, longitudinal changes need to be measured to capture the attributes of empowerment and psychological wellbeing.

Second, future studies should adopt multi-level analysis. Empowerment can be considered in terms of organizational-level atmospheres as well as individual perceptions, and psychological well-being may be differently perceived by public and private sector. Four, Multi-level analysis is needed to account for these differences.

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